

Syntheses of 1,5-Benzothiazepines. Part-VII.

Syntheses of 8-Substituted-2,5-dihydro-

4-(*p*-anisyl)-2-phenyl-1,5-benzothiazepines

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IN continuation of our studies on substituted 1,5-benzothiazepines with substituents in the fused benzene ring, we report here the synthesis of a few 8-substituted-2,5-dihydro-4-(*p*-anisyl)-2-phenyl-1,5-benzothiazepines.

The appropriately substituted 2-aminobenzethiols (1a-f), prepared by literature methods¹, and benzal-4'-methoxyacetophenone (2) on being refluxed together in toluene provided satisfactory yields of the desired 1,5-benzothiazepines (3a-f, Table 1) in a single step (Scheme 1). In the ir spectra, the absence of a band at 1612-1602 cm⁻¹, characteristic feature of 1,4- and 1,5-benzodiazepines and 1,5-benzothiazepines having the C=N grouping² showed that

Scheme 1

C=N is not present in the products. The absorption at 3210-3190 cm⁻¹ showed, instead, the presence of NH. As revealed from the nmr spectra, the tautomeric imine structure corresponding to the enamine form (3), the former showing a multiplet centered around δ 1.5 due to C-3 protons, exists to a very small extent in chloroform solution. In the mass spectra of 3a and 3f, *m/z* *M*⁺ peaks at 363 and 389 respectively, correspond to their molecular weights. 3c showed *M*⁺, [*M*+2]⁺ and [*M*+4]⁺ peaks at 423, 425 and 427 of almost equal intensity which indicate the presence of bromine, and 3b gave the corresponding peaks at 379, 381 and 383, the latter two of

almost 1/3rd intensity of the molecular ion peak [M^+], affirmed the presence of chlorine in 3b.

Experimental

All m.ps. are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were taken on a Perkin-Elmer Infracord-577 spectrometer and ^1H nmr spectra (CDCl_3) on a Jeol FT NMR spectrometer (90 MHz) using TMS as internal standard.

Benzal-4'-methoxyacetophenone (2): Equimolar quantities (0.05 mol) of benzaldehyde (5.30 g) and 4-methoxyacetophenone (7.50 g) were stirred in ethanol at 25° , and to it excess of 10% NaOH solution was added with external cooling. The resulting solid was crystallised from alcohol as yellow crystals (7.5 g, 63%), m.p. 106° (lit.³ 107°).

4-(p-Anisyl)-8-fluoro-2,5-dihydro-2-phenyl-1,5-benzothiazepine (3a): A mixture of 2-amino-5-fluorobenzenethiol (1a, 0.001 mol) and benzal-4'-methoxyacetophenone (2; 0.001 mol) was refluxed in toluene (10 ml) for 3 h when the reaction mixture turned orange. Removal of toluene under reduced pressure gave an orange residue which was washed with petroleum ether (b.p. $60-80^\circ$) and crystallised from ethanol as orange needles (0.16 g, 45%), m.p. 87° . Compounds 3b-f were similarly prepared (Table 1).

TABLE I—PHYSICAL AND ^1H nmr SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 3a-f*

Compd. no.	Yield %	M.p. $^\circ\text{C}$	δ (CDCl_3)			
			5-H (br, s)	2-H (d, 7Hz)	3-H and Ph (m)	OCH_3 (s)
3a	45	87	3.86	6.04	6.32-7.44	3.58
3b	58	97	3.80	6.12	6.40-7.28	3.72
3c	48	87	3.88	5.96	6.44-7.32	3.68
3d ^a	62	85	3.78	5.97	6.28-7.24	3.56
3e ^b	53	70	3.96	6.16	6.20-7.20	3.56
3f ^c	65	100	3.94	5.92	6.16-7.36	3.62

*All the compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses.

^a PhCH_2 appeared at δ 1.96 (s); ^b PhOCH_2 at δ 3.60 (s); ^c PhOC_2H_5 at δ 4.80 (2H, q, OCH_2CH_2) and 1.20 (3H, t, OCH_2CH_2).

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